

FORMING THE METHODOLOGY OF SELF-PERSONALIZATION OF STUDENTS IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE CREDIT MODULE SYSTEM

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Abstract: In the credit-modular system, the main and auxiliary concepts of independent work of students were developed, as well as the deepening of their interest in independent knowledge of science.

Keywords: self-personalization; credit module; nonstandard test.

About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

The credit-module system is a process of educational organization and is an assessment model based on a set of module technologies and a credit measure. A module is a part of the curriculum in which several subjects and courses are studied. It is a set of several subjects aimed at students' ability to acquire certain knowledge and skills, analytical and logical observation. In this, the teacher organizes the educational process, gives live, video and audio lectures, coordinates and monitors the student's activities. The student learns the subject independently and completes the assigned tasks. According to foreign experience, the educational process in the credit-module system consists of 2-4 modules per semester. The subjects collected in the module are formed from easy to complex, from theoretical-methodical subjects to applied subjects and logically based on the principle of complementing each other. In order for a student to become a specialist, it is necessary not only to acquire information, but also to be able to process it and put it into practice.

Over the past 25 years, efforts have been made to integrate technology into teaching and learning. In particular, the personalized learning approach has sought to leverage technology to deliver instruction that is adaptive to the learner and personalized learning environments were used as tools in tailoring instruction to match learner needs. Typically, personalized instruction has been delivered using technology, such as the computer. However, little research has focused on using personalized learning as a tool for remediation. The goal of this study was to empirically investigate the efficacy of personalized learning in Algebra as a remediation tool. This study used a mixed-methods approach to analyze satisfaction with the learning environment, perception of and attitudes toward the

content being delivered, and the reported overall experience and the personalized experience in the context of two versions of a computer-based multimedia learning environment.

Personalized learning is a teaching and learning approach which is centered on the needs, aptitudes, and interests of individual learners. While it is not a new concept, it has gathered increased popularity in the last 10 years or so in a number of countries, including United Kingdom, United States of America, Australia, and New Zealand. It has been promoted as a key learning approach to prepare young people for the demands of the twenty-first century and the expectations placed on them by society. Nowhere is this more true than in the area of vocational learning. In the United Kingdom, personalized learning has been an offshoot of a broader set of reforms aimed at customizing public services to respond specifically to the diverse needs of individuals. In other places personalized learning has evolved from policies aimed at ensuring equality of opportunity for all students. Here it has focused on helping students from minority groups reach their maximum potential.

Socio-economic development of Uzbekistan determines the radical improvement of higher educational system. The importance of personnel training increases, conditions for retraining of higher education specialists at the level of international standards are created. Proceeding from natural requirements of social life and economy, one of the main tasks of modernization of higher educational system is introduction of modern forms and technologies in training on the basis of studying international experience. In order to identify priority areas of systemic reform of higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, raising the process of training independently thinking highly qualified personnel with modern knowledge and high spiritual and moral qualities to a new level, modernization of higher education, development of social sphere and sectors of the economy based on advanced educational technologies, the decree of President Sh. M. Mirziyoyev "On approval of the Concept of Higher Educational System Development" dated October 8, 2019 No. PD-5847 was adopted. Initially, according to the Concept of development of higher education credit-module system should be introduced in 16% of higher educational institutions in 2023, in 57% - in 2025 and 85% – in 2030. The goals of the credit-module system are to expand access to higher education, increase the mobility of students and faculty, and orient curricula and programs toward obtaining the qualifications demanded in the labor market. This system is attractive because it provides comparability of educational programs of different universities and contributes to the harmonization of educational systems with European countries. The credit-module system facilitates the mobility of students and teachers and simplifies the transition from one university to another, determining the amount of work done on the entire academic workload. Moreover,

the very essence of modularization is that students are at center of the teaching-learning process. It calls for a classroom environment in which students are actively engaged in knowledge construction process and a shift in the role of instructor from knowledge transmitter to a facilitator of students' learning. Not only that, modularization requires continuous follow-up and assessment of students' progress throughout the module/course. The practice of effective continuous assessment allows instructors making adjustments to teaching and learning in response to assessment evidence. This also helps students receive feedback about their learning with advice on what they can do to improve. In other words, the implementation modularized curriculum shall ensure the realization of active learning and continuous assessment in higher education institutions.

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